

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D2.7 Technical Report & Database – Update

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D2.3 Technical report

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1 Executive Summary

The COVINFORM project investigates the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic across the 27 EU member states (MS) and the UK. National, regional, and local responses varied in success due to the changeable nature of the public health crisis and the level of preparedness and adaptability of governing institutions. Whilst the general population in the EU and UK experienced disruptive and life changing consequences, the impacts were not equally experienced, and notable differences were evidenced in certain social clusters. In the COVINFORM project we pay particular focus on those vulnerable and marginalised groups. One of the projects outputs includes an interactive risk assessment dashboard that centres on various types of vulnerability (i.e., physical, social, economic and information) and the related consequences, within the context of COVID-19. Extensive work was undertaken to appropriately define the risk assessment framework, this provides a risk score for MS and the UK and is visualised on the risk assessment dashboard. This included engagement with all project stakeholders to inform the various types of indicators that are best used to quantitatively represent key domains, such as social vulnerability, within the context of COVID-19. This was after a review of the literature and finally the identification of such data routinely collected in the EU and UK. Following data collection, the secondary data were preprocessed for in-depth modelling that will provide insights for various stakeholders (e.g., policy makers, first responders and researchers). For example, the contribution of certain features of vulnerability which are highly correlated to the consequences of COVID-19, such as poorer physical health or dependency on social supports. These insights will offer stakeholders the opportunity to explore their assumptions of risk, particularly for vulnerable groups, during public health crisis and ultimately inform their future responses.

This report provides an update of the technical work undertaken in the development of the risk assessment model and the interactive dashboard. The first iteration of this report was submitted in M20 (June 2022), D2.3 'Technical Report'. In addition, this report provides an update of the COVINFORM database which contains both primary and secondary data sources. This provides an update of D2.1, 'Database containing different data sources', submitted in M10 (August 2021). This report includes information regarding activities relating to the collection and processing of national level quantitative data across the EU27 MS and the UK. This data is supplemented with COVINFORM qualitative case study data from the ten COVINFORM target countries (Austria, Belgium, England, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, and Wales). This primary data allows for consideration of the impacts and response of COVID-19 on vulnerable groups as defined by the case studies. A detailed overview of the indicators and data sources integrated into the risk model under the domains of threat, vulnerability, consequences, and resilience are also included in the Annex of this report. In addition, we describe the process followed to download, clean, and reformat data before ingestion into our risk model. We also describe how the risk framework is mapped to our modelling procedure, as well as provide technical details of this modelling and how we compute countries' preliminary risk scores. We also present a summary overview of the interactive dashboard's implementation, encompassing details about its features, design methodology, deployment procedures and accessibility considerations. Additionally, we provide illustrative screenshots of each tab, highlighting their distinct functionalities.

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Terminology

Term	Description
Feature	A measurable piece of data used for analysis or computation.
Values	Individual data, numbers or labels that make up features.
Data lake	A centralised repository that hosts multiple data types in both structured and unstructured formats.
Data frame	Data structure that organises data into a 2D arrangement of named rows and columns, like a spreadsheet.

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Data pipeline	A set of processes and actions that converts raw data into interpretable knowledge or results.
Imputation	The process of replacing missing values dataset with substituted values, estimated by using other available information in the dataset.
Indicator	An indicator is the representation of data for a specified time, place or any other relevant characteristic, corrected for at least one dimension (usually size) to allow for meaningful comparisons. ¹
Normalisation	The statistical process to adjust values measured on different scales to a common scale or range to increase comparability among values and reducing the effect of certain anomalies in the data.
Outlier	In statistics, an outlier is an observation that lies an abnormal distance from other values in a random sample from a population.

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
CSV	Comma separated values (a text file for storing tabular data, delineated by commas)
ECDC	European Center for Disease prevention and Control
ECAD	European Climate Assessment & Dataset
EEA	European Environment Agency
LOCF	Last Observation Carried Forward
MAR	Missing at Random
MCAR	Missing Completely at Random
MICE	Multiple Imputation by Chained Equations
MNAR	Missing Not at Random
MS	Member State
TSV	Tab separated values (a text file for storing tabular data, delineated by tabs)
TVCR	Threat, vulnerability, Consequence, Resilience
WHO	World Health Organization

¹<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/>

2 Introduction

This deliverable describes the technical information related to the data collection and processing activities, model development and evaluation, and dashboard development as part of WP2 ‘Risk assessment model to evaluate the response and impact at different geographical levels’. It provides a final update of data collection activities and the selection of relevant indicators that informed the risk assessment framework as well as releasing the COVINFORM Risk Index developed using this framework. As described in *D2.1 Database containing different data sources*², we reviewed numerous datasets and risk assessment frameworks and finalised our risk assessment methodology. This framework includes COVID-19 related data (i.e., public health surveillance data such as COVID-19 deaths and vaccination rates) and data describing the wider risk environment (e.g., healthcare resources and the public’s level of trust in government). These indicators were selected based on literature review (D2.1. and Annex 1) and stakeholder consultation, for quantification of vulnerabilities that were pre-existing or as a direct or indirect result of COVID-19. Extending on this work, qualitative data sources (e.g., case study interview transcripts and lessons learnt) at local levels in the ten case study sites (WP3) add a layer of contextual knowledge. Case study data will present the voices of members of various subgroups at a local level who were deemed to be at increased risk during COVID-19. Lessons learnt and policy recommendations from those vulnerable subgroups will be presented on a dedicated page on the COVINFORM dashboard.

The dashboard will provide access to the COVINFORM Risk Index, integrate data streams, indices and indicators, maps, and models, including primary research conducted by the COVINFORM project partners and integrated qualitative case study findings. The dashboard will also offer a library of knowledge obtained over the duration of the project, in the form of a Knowledge Repository. The approach taken for the COVINFORM Knowledge Repository will be further outlined in D8.7, ‘COVINFORM COVID-19 Knowledge Repository’ due M36.

² Available online at <https://www.covinform.eu/project-outputs/technical-reports/>

Figure 1. High level COVINFORM risk assessment dashboard development pipeline.

A flow diagram showing the full process, from data requirements definition to data collection and visualisation in the dashboard is pictured above (Figure 1). After having defined the risk framework, we mapped the framework domains and subdomains to quantitative indicators and identified suitable sources of data containing these indicators. This was an iterative process as lack of suitable data sources for some indicators required identifying alternative indicators that could reflect the required risk dimensions. Data for the indicators is collected from different open-source repositories, cleaned and harmonised (see Annex 1 for motivation for choosing each indicator, data source and performed processing). The indicators are then modelled into the COVINFORM Risk Index (a composite statistical indicator). Analysis and validation of the Risk Index were performed to refine the modelling approach. Clean and harmonised indicators are stored in a database alongside Risk Index results (e.g., risk scores for each country). The dashboard retrieves these data to generate different interactive visualisations.

In Section 3, the updated D2.1, 'Database containing different data sources', data identification and collection strategy is described, covering the data source search strategy and eligibility criteria as well as details on the data sources and data coverage. Section 4 provides an update on the database architecture, introducing the final diagram of the COVINFORM data lake. Section 5 describes the data preprocessing activities undertaken to make the data 'useable' for risk modelling. The risk assessment methodology is described in Section 6 and the technical steps to build and validate the COVINFORM Risk Index are detailed in Section 7. Section 8 reports the relation between the risk modelling activities and WP3 case studies. Section 9 provides an update on the COVINFORM dashboard development activities. Section 10 includes details on the software tools used for the different activities in WP2. Finally, conclusions and next steps are presented.

3 Data collection

Prior to identification of relevant data sources and indicators, a thematic lens was applied to group the domains of interest, where insights would result. This required the 'population' of thematic groupings covering government responses and impact, public health responses and impact, citizen and community responses, and inclusive COVID-19 communication. These can be described by multiple relevant indicators as outlined in Table 1 below and has been described in more detail in D2.1.

3.1 Final data source search strategy – alternative sources

Under guidance of risk assessment experts of partner organisation, Factor Social, and feedback from the ten-case study leads, pertinent to their case study populations, the 'baseline' framework was finalised in Spring 2022 (Table 1 and outlined below). Following the finalisation of the COVINFORM Risk Assessment Framework, extensive data collection activities were required to obtain the appropriate data for each EU MS and the UK.

Based on the project's final requirements, the eligibility criteria have been updated since D2.3 [M20]. The inclusion criteria are as follows:

1) As previously reported, **national** level across the EU27 MS and the UK. Open-source data were the primary data sources used (See Annex 1. Indicator Description and Source).

2) Following extensive data review, it became evident that due to varying data collection practices or incomplete/absent data *within* EU member states the current application of a tailored **regional** risk model would be inappropriate, in terms of efficiencies, and comparability and usability. Initial plans to demonstrate the application in a single MS were abandoned due to the degree of missing data and the level of granularity and coverage of indicators.

3) As previously reported, **local levels** pertinent to the case study sites. The relationship between WP2 and WP3 Case Study Research, are described in Section 8 of this report and in D3.4. 'Comparative Analysis'.³ It is widely accepted on the COVINFORM project and in the general research community that quantitative data provides a certain degree of insight/understanding to a problem or phenomena. However, the problem can be experienced differently, by different countries, or groups in society. The qualitative case study data provide opportunity to add context to national risk profiles and describe how "risk" or "vulnerability" can be defined or experienced by various subgroups in society. The data acquired from the local level case study research was interpreted, processed, and ingested into the dashboard as the qualitative data became available (Summer 2023). The final case study results will be submitted in M35 (September 2023) in D3.8 'Final case study reports and comparative report'.

³ Available at <https://www.covinform.eu/project-outputs/technical-reports/>

OBJECT AT RISK (HEALTH)													
	THREAT (RISK OBJECT)			VULNERABILITIES				CONSEQUENCES (IMPACTS)				RESILIENCE	
Time period	Virus (cases)	Variant of concern ¹	Likelihood of dev.	Physical	Social	Economic	Information	Health	Social	Economic	Environmental	Ability to recover	Ability to Adapt
Baseline (2019)	-	-	Mobility index, International Trade, Seaborne and Air passengers, Commercial Airports, Housing Concentration, Pollution, Temperature, Age of population	Hospital beds, ICU beds, Residential beds, Medical Staff, Pre-existing Health Conditions, Older adult population	Education level, Rural vs Urban, Population Density, Gender, Migrant Population, Civic Participation	GDP, % Living in Poverty, Income Inequality, Employment by Industry	Digital Access, Digital Skills, Trust in Government	Excess deaths, Hospital Admissions, ICU Admissions	Food insecurity, Crime	Unemployment Rate, Reduced Income, Social Protection	Exposure to outdoor air pollution, GHG emissions	Government Health Spending, Investments - Gross fixed capital formation, General Government Debt, Corruption Perception Index	-
First Phase (2020)	Weekly case rate, Positivity (%), Testing rate	Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Delta	As above	As above	As above	As above	As above	COVID-19 death rate, Excess Deaths, Hospital Admissions, ICU admissions	Food insecurity, Crime, Loss of Education	As above	As above	Government Health Spending, Investments - Gross fixed capital formation, General Government Debt, Corruption Perception Index, Vaccine Affordability	Economic interventions (import/export support, tax credits, cash transfers, tax delays, lowered central bank interest, wage support and credit schemes), Non pharmaceutical health interventions (masks, curfew, domestic lockdown, state of emergency)
Post-vaccine (2021)	As above, no. of detections of variants, % variant	Gamma, Delta, Omicron	As above, plus COVID-19 vaccination rate	As above	As above	As above	As above	As above	As above	As above	As above	As above	As above

Table 1. Final COVINFORM Risk Assessment Framework

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3.2 Data sources

The specific indicators and their data source are listed in Annex 1. The sources of data utilised were:

- CEDEFOP (<https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en>)
- Civil Aviation Authority UK (CAA) (<https://www.caa.co.uk/>)
- European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) (<https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en>)
- European Climate Assessment & Dataset (ECAD) (<https://www.ecad.eu/>)
- European Environmental Agency (EEA) (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en>)
- Eurobarometer survey (<https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/screen/home>)
- Eurostat (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>)
- Food and Agricultural Organisation (FAO) (<https://www.fao.org/home/en>)
- Google Mobility data (<https://www.google.com/covid19/mobility/>)
- Office of National Statistics (UK) (<https://www.ons.gov.uk/>)
- OECD (<https://data.oecd.org/>)
- Our World Data (<https://ourworldindata.org/>)
- Transparency.org (<https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2022>)
- WHO - Global Health Observatory (<https://www.who.int/data/gho>)
- World Bank (<https://data.worldbank.org/>)

3.3 Data Coverage

Geographic coverage of most indicators is good at the national level. For 2019, all countries have at least 90% of the indicators available. For 2020, the ‘digital skills’ indicator is missing for all countries as the ESS (ICT) survey is conducted every two years (2019 and 2021 available). In 2020, 23 countries have at least 90% of the indicators available with Greece, Luxembourg, Malta having at least 85% of and Republic of Cyprus having 79% of the indicators available. See Figures 2 and 3 for details of indicator availability. Data for 2021 is still under process with some indicators’ processing having to be delayed due to delays in data publishing by the source. In many cases 2021 data was only available with coverage across all MS by early to mid-2023.

Where data were collected from European databases such as Eurostat, ECDC and EEA, the UK had missing data post 2019 or 2020 due to the exit of the UK from European data sharing agreements. In such cases, where possible, comparable data were collected from UK specific sources (see Annex 1 for details). In some cases, such as with the ‘crime’ indicator, UK data had to be collected from sources for the four different countries (England, Wales, Scotland and Northern Ireland) and averaged to produce a single value for the nation. In the case of the ‘housing concentration’ indicator for the UK, only data for England could be gathered.

The coverage across time varies across data sources (see Annex 1) but for the COVINFORM risk model, it was essential that data for 2019, 2020 and 2021 were available. Much of the data are available on a yearly basis. The exceptions are in the case of epidemiological data such as COVID-19 cases, deaths, tests and hospital and ICU occupancy, which are available on a daily or weekly basis.

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Even after extensive searches, there were some cases where certain indicator data were not available. In such cases, the missing data were replaced with values estimates (the procedures followed to obtain these estimated is called imputation procedure and is outlined in [Section 7.3](#).

Figure 2. Image showing data coverage of indicators across domains for 2019. Light blue cells indicate that the indicator value is available for the country, dark blue cells if it's not available, yellow cells indicate that the indicator has yet to be processed.

Figure 3. Image showing data coverage of indicators across domains for 2020. Light blue cells indicate that the indicator value is available for the country, dark blue cells if it's not available, yellow cells indicate that the indicator has yet to be processed.

4 Database Architecture - Update

All the data collected to create the COVINFORM Risk Index are stored in the COVINFORM data lake, hosted on TRI servers. Besides data for the risk modelling, the COVINFORM data lake hosts two types of qualitative data: 1) reports, papers, project's outputs and other documents included in the COVINFORM Knowledge repository and 2) case study data, namely case study descriptions lessons learnt, policy recommendations and selected (and anonymised) interviews quotes.

Figure 4. COVINFORM data lake architecture diagram.

4.1 Data Ingestion

In COVINFORM, data are collected by manual download or by automatic request to an API, depending on the data access modality provided by the data provider. The data are then manually uploaded by an authorised data administrator to the COVINFORM data lake.

4.2 Data Lake

Data at each level of processing (from raw to clean) are stored in the data lake (Figure 1) to keep track of any data modification, prevent and track accidental data losses or unwanted changes and revert to less refined versions of the data as required. Data stored in the COVINFORM data lake move across four *processing zones*. The first zone, the *Raw Zone*, takes the files loaded into the system as they are. After standard cleaning and formatting, the data move to the *Transform Zone*. After data imputation, normalisation and more advanced processing, indicator data are in the final format, ready to be fed to the risk model and can then move to the *Clean Zone*. The outputs of the modelling (risk scores at subdomain and domain levels and final risk score for each country) are stored in the *Insight Zone*. Datasets metadata are stored in the *Meta Zone*.

4.3 Data Privacy and Access

The data lake is hosted on TRI secure servers⁴. All the data visualised and used for modelling is shared by the providers under open-source licences which allow content redistribution and reuse under source attribution. Where explicit consent for data reuse was required, TRI contacted the sources to gain the required authorisations. The data, at different levels of preprocessing and including the relevant documentation to assure reproducibility of the processed data, will be made available by TRI under provision of a written request. The results of the risk modelling (i.e., the COVINFORM Risk Index for each country and single subdomains and domain scores) will be downloadable by the end-users via the dashboard.

5 Data preprocessing

The data preprocessing activities have proceeded in a similar manner as those described in D2.4 'Cloud-based interactive dashboard for displaying geospatial layers'. The addition of new data sources was completed to ensure adequate coverage of the EU27 MS as well as the UK. Since the UK ceased collaboration with European statistical institutions following BREXIT at the end of 2019, most of the UK indicators for 2020 and 2021 have been obtained from a different source than for the EU MS, which raised challenges related to assuring comparability between UK's and the MS's data.

In many instances, due to UK data being collected from different UK-specific national sources, indicator definitions and reporting practices were different than those reported by Eurostat, which assures standardisation in reporting across the MS's sates. Where trends of the UK-specific data were visibly different from the UK data available from European sources pre-Brexit, the data owners were contacted, data accuracy was verified, and the indicator definition confirmed. In addition, some UK data are collected and reported by the four different counties (England, Wales, Scotland and Northern Ireland) separately. This required averaging across the counties data to produce a crude measure for the UK as a whole.

For the new data sources, the data were downloaded, cleaned, reshaped and saved following the same procedure as described in D2.4. All datasets were processed into individual standard data frames⁵ with information including:

- **Indicator description** – Text describing the indicator in the manner described by the source.
- **Country name** – The names of the 27 EU member states and UK were standardised across all datasets and where the two or three letter ISO 3166-1 country codes⁶ were provided, these were converted into their full names.
- **Unit** – The units for which the data were measured (e.g., %GDP, per 1,000 inhabitants etc.).
- **Year/date** - Where available, annual values were used. If the dataset reported daily data (typical when reporting epidemiological data pertaining to COVID-19), the dates were specified in the year-month-day format.
- **Value** - Some datasets included other information such as age, sex, ethnicity, income band etc.

⁴ The COVINFORM data lake is built on Amazon S3, an object storage service that offers industry-leading scalability, data availability, security and performance.

⁵ A data frame is a data structure that organizes data into a 2-dimensional table of rows and columns.

⁶ Available at <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#search>

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Each cleaned and formatted dataset was saved as an individual comma separated value (CSV) file and uploaded onto the COVINFORM data lake to the transform zone.

For each year represented in the framework (2019, 2020, 2021), the individual indicator CSV file was then extracted from the data lake and values for each indicator and year were loaded onto a master data frame corresponding to each subdomain of the framework. Where epidemiological data was available daily or weekly, we have taken the cumulative value on the last available day of the year to extract a single representative value for the year.

At this stage, where a value for an indicator was unavailable for a country from the main indicator source, we replaced the missing data with values taken from other available sources providing the same or a comparable indicator (see Annex 1). To ensure data quality and to maintain data comparability across sources, the trends and values of the same indicator obtained from the main and alternative source were visually inspected. This process also included evaluating the indicator definitions by each data source and checking whether it matched the primary source definition.

In cases where the original data are provided as absolute measures of the indicator, we obtain a relative measure by dividing the data by either population size (per 1,000 inhabitants) or, in the case of financial data by GDP (% GDP). This step allows to get a better sense of differences among countries values for an indicator, without distorting effects caused by countries size and richness. For instance, if we would consider only the absolute figures, larger and densely populated countries will be more likely to have higher values in demographic indicators, similarly, richer countries will systematically have higher values in economic indicators, making the comparison between two countries of very different economic levels meaningless.

A CSV file for each year and subdomain is then saved in the clean zone for further retrieval and processing. These further preprocessing stages are documented in [Section 7.2](#) as they include decisions made and justified in the specific context of the COVINFORM risk model.

6 Risk Assessment Methodology

As outlined in D2.3 'Technical Report', the risk assessment model developed by the COVINFORM project is not intended to predict future outbreaks, forecast the end of the COVID-19 pandemic, or predict when and where an emerging pandemic might emerge. Rather, its aim is to allow for evaluation a-priori of the COVID-19 pandemic, to test hypotheses, explore assumptions, and offer unique community-centred insights⁷, coupled with national level analytics to strategize policy development for other health crisis situations.

Central to the objectives of the COVINFORM project, the response and impacts on vulnerable and marginalised groups have been prioritised and will be validated against the WP3 case study findings. In our risk model we define threat as the risk object, "the virus, or variant of, and the level of transmission due to the built and natural environment" (e.g., pollution, temperature, and housing concentration). The leading 'object at risk' of any health crisis is population health. As observed, the risk exposure was disproportionately experienced and reports of 'clustering' within certain groups were

⁷ Community' as defined by the COVINFORM case studies 'communities of practice' or 'characteristic', not geographic (e.g., migrant frontline workers).

reported widely from the early stages (e.g., BAME, low socioeconomic status, females, migrants, healthcare workers). To ensure inclusive risk modelling, factoring the level of vulnerability of a country and its population, a vulnerability index including factors linked to physical, social, economic and information vulnerabilities and their consequences (impacts) are central to the risk framework. Resilience is defined by the COVINFORM project as a country's ability to recover (e.g., economic activity) and the ability to adapt (e.g., fiscal measures such as income support) overtime. The risk model will provide an index of risk for each COVINFORM partner country, as described in the next section.

7 Building the Risk Index (Data Modelling) - Update

The COVINFORM Risk Index is a composite indicator (i.e., a mathematical combination of indicators into a single value intended to summarise or measure a complex multi-dimensional phenomenon), obtained by *hierarchical* aggregation. This means that single indicators belonging to each subdomain are combined into a first composite indicator (*subdomain score*), the subdomain scores are then combined into a second composite of composite indicators (*domain scores*) and finally the domain scores are combined into the final *risk score* (the final composite indicator).

Figure 5. Hierarchical representation of the risk framework. Note that each subdomain can comprise one or more features, as indicated in Table 1.

For example, given the hierarchic structure of our risk framework (Figure 5), the subdomain score for the subdomain *Social-Consequences* is obtained by combining the indicators *food insecurity* and *crime*; in a similar way subdomain scores for the *health*, *economic* and *environmental* consequences are obtained; all these subdomain scores are combined into the *Consequences* domain score. The procedure is repeated for the other domains and the domain scores are combined into the final composite indicator (the COVINFORM Risk Index).

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More precisely, the COVINFORM Risk Index is a *weighted* composite indicator. In practice, this means that when building the composite, we place on indicators and scores a weight, i.e., a value reflecting the importance of the concept underlying the indicator/score in the composite. Two mathematical formulations commonly used to obtain weighted composite indicators are the *geometric* and *arithmetic* aggregation. We provide two alternatives of the COVINFORM Risk Index, each using arithmetic or geometric aggregation. The formulae for computing the (weighted) final risk score are as follows:

$$r_A = 0.25 * d_V + 0.25 * d_C + 0.25 * d_R + 0.25 * d_T$$

$$r_G = (d_V + 1)^{0.25} * (d_C + 1)^{0.25} * (d_R + 1)^{0.25} * (d_T + 1)^{0.25}$$

Equation 1: The COVINFORM Risk Index formula (arithmetically and geometrically aggregated versions)

r_A and r_G represent the arithmetically and geometrically aggregated scores respectively, whilst equal weights are used for each of the four domains (vulnerability d_V , consequences d_C , resilience d_R , and threat d_T). Further information on these formulae (included generalised versions for other hierarchical levels within the risk model) is available in Section [7.6 Aggregation](#).

The details on the derivation of the overall COVINFORM Risk Index, domain, and subdomains scores are provided in D2.3., submitted in June 2022. The overall methodology to obtain the Risk Index stayed unchanged but we made modifications to various stages of the risk index processing pipeline (including imputation and normalisation) for the indicators before aggregation into the subdomain composite. The new weighting strategy and rationale behind its choice is reported later in this section. Note also that scores are computed separately for each country and for each time period in our framework, therefore a risk score for baseline, first-phase, and post-vaccine periods (2019, 2020, and 2021) will be obtained, allowing for drawing insights on the change of the risk score over time.

Following the data preprocessing steps, imputation, transformation, and normalisation of the indicator data is necessary before computing the subdomain scores. Different modelling decisions can lead to different scores, and a sensitivity and robustness analysis should be performed to assess the impact of these modelling decisions and consider, alongside the rationality of these decisions, the optimal choices. In other words, we want to identify the sources of uncertainty in our composite index and assess how they affect the multiple levels of risk scores. Where assessment by domain experts is not possible, common practice in the composite index space and best judgement have been used to make suitable modelling decisions. Initial efforts towards these validation activities are reported in the last paragraph of this section.

7.1 Correlation between Indicators

Computing a correlation (Pearson) matrix of continuous indicators allows us to consider the relations between the information they provide. If two indicators are highly correlated (having a Pearson correlation coefficient greater than 0.85⁸), they are providing similar information to the composite

⁸ Marvel, S. W., House, J. S., Wheeler, M., Song, K., Zhou, Y.-H., Wright, F. A., Chiu, W. A., Rusyn, I., Motsinger-Reif, A., & Reif, D. M. (2021). The COVID-19 Pandemic Vulnerability Index (PVI) Dashboard: Monitoring County-Level Vulnerability Using Visualization, Statistical Modeling, and Machine Learning. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 129(1), 017701. <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP8690>

index. For example, both income distribution and poverty rate data may provide information on financial hardship across a population – if highly correlated, a model that uncritically aggregates this data may place more emphasis on financial hardship as a risk factor than intended. As one input should not be weighted unequally against another (as expanded on in [Weighting, Section 7.5](#)) the default approach is to adjust the weighting of these indicators in aggregation, though one of the highly correlated indicators may also be removed entirely from the subdomain risk score computation.

7.2 Indicator Preprocessing

Several transformations need to be performed on indicators before they can be used to compute risk scores. Zero values and data such as ‘not_applicable’ strings are standardised; where necessary, scales are inverted: for each indicator we want a consistent direction i.e., “the lower the value the better”, which is achieved by simply multiplying data values by -1 for indicators where higher values are “better”. Deciding which direction is “better” for each indicator is not always obvious and largely context (subdomain) dependent. For example, a high number of aircraft passengers might be a positive if we are looking to evaluate the development of a country’s transport industry (higher values are better), but a negative if we are looking to evaluate the exposure of a country to viral spread (lower values are better).

Lastly, some indicators will possess outliers: identifying these outliers is non-trivial, and we have adopted the approach recommended by the European Commission’s Joint Research Centre⁹ and implemented in the Transitions Performance Index 2021¹⁰. This involves computing a dataset’s *skewness* and *kurtosis*, measures of the asymmetry and “tailedness” of the dataset’s distribution, respectively. A dataset (in the case of the risk index, an indicator) can be considered to possess outliers if it has an absolute skewedness of greater than 2 and a kurtosis of greater than 3.5. It is important to handle these outliers before normalisation: as normalisation processes like rescaling seek to convert indicators to a standard range, the normalised indicator can be distorted if the minima and maxima are outliers.

For the COVINFORM Risk Index, each indicator meeting the criteria outlined above will be *log-transformed* (i.e., the indicators values are replaced by their logarithm) before normalisation. Due to the presence of negative values (which cannot be log-transformed), we must first make all values positive whilst preserving the range, for which the following formula was used:

$$x' = \log \log (x - (x) + a), \quad \text{where } a = 0.01((x) - (x))$$

Equation 2: Log transformation function adjusted to handle negative values.

⁹ Damioli, G. (2018, November 5). *Step 3: The identification and treatment of outliers* [Slideshow]. COIN 2018 - 16th JRC Annual Training on Composite Indicators & Scoreboards, Ispra, Italy. <https://composite-indicators.jrc.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/COIN%202018%20Step%203%20Outliers%20and%20Missing%20data.pdf>

¹⁰ Prevost, S., Benavente, D., Stevenson, A., Caperna, G., & Panella, F. (2022). *Transitions Performance Index 2021: Towards fair and prosperous sustainability*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2777/09602>

7.3 Imputation

Following preprocessing there are still some indicators with missing values that cannot be imputed in bulk using 'Last Observation Carried Forward' (LOCF) or similar techniques based on data from previous years. The most suitable imputation technique for each indicator depends primarily on whether the data is 'missing completely at random' (MCAR), 'missing at random' (MAR), or 'missing not at random' (MNAR), as well as the correlation between indicators in a subdomain. These factors will determine the most appropriate imputation method missing for a given indicator.

The most frequently used imputation method in the COVINFORM risk index is the Multiple Imputation by Chained Equations (MICE) approach, used for those indicators where data were historically unavailable in a given country, or where the reasons for this lack of data collection were deemed independent of the other indicators in the subdomain, rendering the data either MCAR or MAR. A MICE approach is also dependent on other indicators in the given subdomain providing sufficient information to impute a similar value: for example, the number of doctors, hospital beds, and healthcare spending could reasonably be used to derive a statistical estimate of the number of nurses employed in a given year.

Other variables are not possible to impute, due to a lack of data for multiple years and little correlation between other present indicators. For example, international trade and adult population data could not reasonably be used to impute temperature data. In this case, temperature data would simply be ignored for this country/year combination when calculating a risk score, and the weights for other indicators adjusted accordingly.

7.4 Normalisation

There are a number of normalisation methods which are commonly used in composite indexes, and which is preferable depends on a number of factors, particularly the level of compensability (to what degree one indicator can "compensate" for the deficiencies of another, and hence how indicators may reflect the same information or "dimension" of an underlying phenomena) that is desired in different subdomains.

R-scaling, otherwise known as min-max normalisation, is used on all indicators across all subdomains. This method reduces the range of all indicators to (0, 1). Another common normalisation method, standardisation, was also considered. Standardisation makes indicators on different scale more easily comparable by transforming the data so that they have the same mean and the same measure of spread standard deviation.

Re-scaling was selected as it is less likely to reward exceptional behaviour in one indicator than standardisation, preferring an "average" score in many indicators to exceptional scores in a few. This is in-line with the goals expressed in the production of the COVINFORM risk model: namely, the desired focus on complex systems analysis that requires a data analysis that respects the importance of emergent and intersecting risk over and above risk in isolated domains. Other normalisation techniques considered include rankings (inappropriate due to ignoring degrees of difference between countries, which would be especially stark considering the small datasets in use) and categorical scores (which would require a broad range of expert input).

The possibility of using ‘goalposts’ (upper and lower normalisation bounds), as in the Transitions Performance Index 2021¹¹, was examined but disregarded due to the need for expert input. This would allow for indicator values outside set ‘goalposts’ to be set to standard values, and hence the range of normalised values to be less impacted by outliers. Likewise, the possibility of using different normalisation techniques for different subdomains was considered but disregarded, as this would create disparity between risk scores in different subdomains. Whilst not an issue when computing higher-level scores due to re-normalisation, it would likely cause confusion and lack of comparability for users of the COVINFORM dashboard, who would be able to view subdomain-level risk scores.

At present, only indicator data is normalised when calculating subdomain scores – scores are not re-normalised when calculating domain and overall risk scores; this will be subject to further review in the final stages of risk modelling in September 2023.

7.5 Weighting

Weights dictate the level of “influence” an indicator will have in each subdomain, and hence should represent the value we place upon each indicator, both in terms of importance and how one indicator may compensate for an information deficit in another. This is a challenging process, and several methods can be used in selecting indicator weights when building a composite index, each with their advantages and disadvantages. In constructing the COVINFORM Risk Index two key factors determining our choice were:

- Feasibility of expert judgement: due to the time and budget constraints of the project, the ability to access a suitable pool of domain experts across all required domains, and to conduct a form of multi-criteria decision analysis or a Delphi consensus approach was disregarded.
- Statistical considerations: the size of our sample is 28 (the number of countries for which we have data), a sample size deemed too small for computing statistically derived weights (e.g., using principal component analysis or factor analysis) with sufficient statistical significance.

Most composite indexes rely on equal weighting, implying that all indicators have the same “worth”. This is also the approach we have adopted for the COVINFORM Risk Index. The only exception to this is where two indicators in each subdomain are highly correlated (as defined in [Correlation between Indicators \(Section 7.1\)](#)): in this case they are treated as a single indicator for the purposes of dividing weights between indicators, with this weight then divided between them. For example, if a given subdomain has five indicators, two of which are highly correlated, the weights of the respective indicators may be given as: [0.25, 0.25, 0.25, 0.125, 0.125].

7.6 Aggregation

For reasons outlined in [Weighting \(Section 7.5\)](#) the choice of aggregation method should not rely on expert judgement. As subdomains have different numbers of indicators aggregation will inevitably provide some indicators with more “importance” than others when computing domain-level risk scores and final risk scores. The level of skew of this sort must be carefully accounted for, including setting limits of what level we are willing to accept, and putting into practice mitigation strategies where possible.

¹¹ Transitions Performance Index 2021, <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/50fff167-a34e-11ec-83e1-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

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In the case of the COVINFORM Risk Index linear aggregation (e.g., arithmetic, the sum of weighted indicators) can be meaningfully applied, providing that all indicators are scaled consistently via normalisation (so that they can be meaningfully compared). Linear aggregations reward indicators proportionally to their weight and are easy to interpret but they imply full compensability (meaning that poor performance of some indicators might be compensated for by sufficiently high values in other indicators). This is not always desirable and non-compensatory methods would indeed be adequate in our case. However, they are time-consuming to implement due to reliance on expert judgments and have therefore been excluded. A non-linear approach like geometric aggregation (i.e., the product of weighted indicators) could, in our case, be a valid option to allow some degree of non-compensability while ensuring simplicity of computation (since expert judgement is not required). Geometric aggregation also has the benefit of rewarding improvement (higher scores) in indicators with lower means, more than it does identical improvement/score increase in indicators with higher means, which is useful in the context of lowering risk. For this reason, we have chosen to produce risk scores both arithmetically and geometrically for the user's analysis.

Single path aggregation is preferred when computing the risk model. For example, only subdomain-level risk scores calculated using arithmetic aggregation are used when calculating domain-level risk scores using arithmetic aggregation, and likewise for geometric aggregation.

The formulae for the arithmetically and geometrically aggregated scores respectively are as follows:

$$r_A = \text{sum}(r'_A \odot w)$$

$$r_G = \text{prod}((r'_G + 1)^w)$$

Equation 3: General weighted arithmetic and geometric means functions

Arithmetically aggregated scores (r_A) for each country are computed as the sum of $r'_A \odot w$ where r'_A is the series of arithmetically aggregated scores from each domain and w provides the associated weights for each domain. \odot defines a simple element-wise multiplication of these components: for example, $[1,2] \odot [2,3] = [2,6]$. The sum of this resulting list is then the overall arithmetic score for that country. For geometrically aggregated scores (r_G), terms are defined similarly to above, with the subscript G denoting the use of geometrically aggregated domain scores. The use of min-max normalisation to provide indicators with a common scale and aligned distribution (outlined in [Normalisation](#)) requires the addition of 1 to each score: this preserves the range of the data but ensures each value is greater than 1, ensuring that weights are applied appropriately. The resulting list is then multiplied element-by-element to produce the resulting score. This approach is applied across the index hierarchy, with domain scores computed from subdomains and subdomains from indicator data.

7.7 Ranking

Risk scores at the domain and overall levels are ranked to provide a basic and accessible comparison of risk between countries. While the overall ranking provides an average assessment of a country's risk, rankings at domain level can provide interesting insights on countries profiles across the different

dimensions of risk. Ranking is not performed at the subdomain level as subdomains do not contain sufficient information value to be able to have a meaningful ranking – without the additional context available at the domain level and above, such outputs may be misleading. Rankings are produced using both arithmetic and geometric aggregation, and these ranks are then further used to divide the index countries into quintiles¹² (five sets).

These rankings and quintile assignments are less information-dense than the risk scores themselves due to the removal of detail such as how close one country's risk may be to another's but are nevertheless useful in producing diagrammatic, visual, and interactive outputs (as in the form of the COVINFORM Dashboard) and being easy to understand and communicate. For this reason, the quintile assignments for each country may be considered the 'final output' of the COVINFORM risk model, by providing a categorical "high-low" style label to each country, and in each domain.

Figure 6. Colour-coded risk assessment choropleth within the Risk Assessment tab in the dashboard.

7.8 Robustness, Sensitivity and Validation

Interpretations of correctness and quality in composite indexes are varied and often ambiguous¹³, making evaluation challenging. Often there is little or no data that can be considered a 'ground truth' against which to evaluate aggregates, making choices such as weighting and normalisation technique difficult to statistically justify. However, this is less true of the COVINFORM risk index, which can consider data from the COVID-19 pandemic and use it to validate the correctness of aggregated risk scores, an analysis conducted in similar studies¹⁴. We have made use of data recording cumulative

¹² Quintiles are used to create cut-off points for a given population. The first quintile represents the lowest fifth of the data (1% to 20%); the second quintile represents the second fifth (21% to 40%) and so on.

¹³ Walesiak, M. (2018). The choice of normalization method and rankings of the set of objects based on composite indicator values. *Statistics in Transition New Series*, 19, 693–710. <https://doi.org/10.21307/stattrans-2018-036>

¹⁴ Marvel, S. W., House, J. S., Wheeler, M., Song, K., Zhou, Y.-H., Wright, F. A., Chiu, W. A., Rusyn, I., Motsinger-Reif, A., & Reif, D. M. (2021). The COVID-19 Pandemic Vulnerability Index (PVI) Dashboard: Monitoring County-Level Vulnerability Using Visualization, Statistical Modeling, and Machine Learning. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 129(1), 017701. <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP8690>

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deaths caused by COVID-19 (as defined by our data source¹⁵ and adjusted for population) as the primary response variable against which to validate the risk model. Additional variables considered in this evaluation process are the cumulative case, testing, and positivity rates (adjusted for population).

Such validation can only be conducted with synchronous data for the years 2020 and 2021, as there are no known cases of COVID-19 in Europe before 2020. However, validation of 2019 data can be performed as an assessment of how indicators affect pandemic preparedness and hence mitigate future risk. Initial validation consisted of calculating the Pearson and Kendall rank correlation coefficients of the arithmetically and geometrically aggregated risk scores and cumulative death statistics (taken on 31st December in the respective years), as well as other response variables. Note that the 'Virus' subdomain includes the case, testing, and positivity rate variables by default, and hence when these variables are used in validation, they are excluded from the risk model - it is expected that a strong correlation among epidemiological COVID-19 indicators and the chosen response variable would distort the validation outcomes. In other words, a high correlation between the COVIFORM Risk Index and the response variable (which would provide the empirical validation of the index we are seeking) would be effectively driven by the correlation among epidemiological indicators, preventing us from making a useful assessment of the value of including other domains' indicators in the model.

This initial validation did not produce statistically significant results in most domain-variable pairings at this stage. This is to be expected, due to the aforementioned challenges in determining optimal weighting, normalisation, and most notably scale inversion, the non-trivial task of assessing whether an increase in a particular indicator will have a positive or negative affect on overall risk. This is primarily due to the complexity and contradictory nature of the information captured by many indicators (as demonstrated in the example in [Indicator Preprocessing \(Section 7.2\)](#) of the number of aircraft passengers both providing information on the development of a country's transport industry and its exposure to viral spread), but the additional dimension of how this balance may change during a pandemic must also be considered. As another example, whilst the number of hospital beds may be a useful indicator in assessing healthcare outcomes and pandemic preparedness, suggesting more hospital beds would reduce risk, an increase may also indicate a worsening domestic epidemic and increasing case rates. Considering how these indicators should be assessed when aggregated across an entire year is a challenging task, and validation of the type outlined here permits a quantitative evaluation of the impact of indicator scale inversion on response variables.

Notable improvements will be made to this validation process over the next few months and will permit the optimisation and fine-tuning of input factors including normalisation, weighting, and indicator scale inversion. As well as the inclusion of additional data, we intend to conduct an examination of correlation across time and a significantly more complete statistical analysis including assessments at the subdomain level and simulation analyses for optimisation and uncertainty analysis.

Given the difficulty of performing correctness validation, many developers of composite index opt to assess robustness instead of, or in addition to, correctness, which may be aided by uncertainty and sensitivity analysis¹⁶. Uncertainty analysis examines how uncertainty in input factors (including data

¹⁵ <https://ourworldindata.org/covid-deaths#deaths-from-covid-19-background>

¹⁶ Nardo, M., Saisana, M., Saltelli, A., Tarantola, S., Hoffman, A., & Giovannini, E. (2008). *Handbook on Constructing Composite Indicators: Methodology and User Guide* (C. Stevens, G. Baygan, K. Olsen, & S. Moore,

error, weighting and normalisation schemes, and indicator selection) can propagate across the composite index. Sensitivity is a product of uncertainty in these factors and is an assessment of how individual indicators contribute to variance in the output caused by uncertainty. Uncertainty in composite indexes is unavoidable¹⁷, and the purpose of this analysis is to demonstrate that a given composite index is robust in the sense that it is not statistically significantly biased by input factors such as indicator selection or the weighting method used, as well as to provide evidenced reasoning behind choices made.

This analysis can be difficult and lacks thorough research. This is due to a combination of factors including poor understanding of data error at source, as well as the previously mentioned difficulties in locating ‘ground truth’ data that may be used in such analysis. For the COVINFORM Risk Index, uncertainty and sensitivity analysis will be explored more extensively before the final dashboard release (November 2023). Initial efforts in this direction looked at measures of how individual indicators contribute to aggregates at the subdomain level and above, an example of which is presented in the figure below.

Indicator Contributions towards Geometric Score (Log-scaled)

Figure 7. A spider/radar chart displaying indicator contributions to the Likelihood of Development subdomain geometrically-aggregated risk score. Chart is calculated using equal weights, min-max normalisation, and is log-scaled.

8 WP2 relation to Case Study Research (WP3)

The quantitative methods applied in the risk assessment model allows for generalisability; however, it may omit the complete picture of risk for marginalised or vulnerable sub-groups in the population. The findings of the ten COVINFORM case studies (WP3) will be reported in September 2023 [M35] of the project. The findings will provide insights into the lived experiences of those at increased risk during the COVID-19 pandemic. For example, migrant nurses, members of minority communities and elderly living in care homes. This process offers an extra layer of contextual insights which are commonly overlooked or reduced by quantitative methods alone. Each COVINFORM case study lead

Eds.). OECD Publishing.

<https://www.oecd.org/els/soc/handbookonconstructingcompositeindicatorsmethodologyanduserguide.htm>

¹⁷ Kovacevic, M., & García Agaña, C. (2010). Uncertainty and Sensitivity Analysis of the Human Development Index. *UNDP (United Nations Development Programme)*. <https://hdr.undp.org/content/uncertainty-and-sensitivity-analysis-human-development-index>

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identified key quotes from their research interviews with participants of vulnerable groups (as defined by the research team). The interviewees were asked to speak of their experiences of the pandemic, in terms of risks, vulnerabilities and resilience factors. This process provided an opportunity for the case study participants to define their own vulnerabilities (if any), their perception of risk and ways in which they adapted to the challenges faced because of the pandemic. This will allow for deeper insights to be reported and descriptive experiences to accompany the risk profiles of various groups during COVID-19. For example, the risk framework may indicate that women are more vulnerable to the consequences of COVID-19, but it does not explain the reasons of the effect and their meanings in certain contexts. A summary of the data collected from the case studies, lessons learnt, and policy recommendations will be presented in the dashboard.

9 Dashboard

We will provide a demonstrator of the dashboard in deliverable D2.9 due in October 2023 (M36) which will include a technical report with details on the dashboard features, design processes, deployment steps as well as accessibility consideration. We provide here a summary of the dashboard technical features and some screenshots of the current dashboard.

- The COVINFORM dashboard is a dynamic and interactive dashboard, built utilising Dash, a Python web framework, to visually represent the key findings and insights.
- The dashboard runs on an EC2 (Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud) hosted by Trilateral.
- This dashboard is designed as a multi-page application to accommodate multiple features which can be accessed via the available links within the dashboard or by directly visiting its unique URL.
- We ensure that the entire application strictly adheres to the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.0 AA accessibility standards¹⁸ throughout the feature implementation process.
- Dash Bootstrap Components¹⁹, an open-source front-end framework used for designing and developing responsive websites and web applications, was used as a design library to keep colour schemes and component designs consistent across the dashboard.
- The plots displayed in each tab can be download by the user as a HTML file.

The Dashboard currently entails seven tabs:

Homepage: This is the default page when the dashboard is launched/visited. It provides information about the Dashboard with a quick summary of the project, a short description on the functionality of what each tab provides.

¹⁸ W3C (2008). *Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.0*. [online] W3.org. Available at: <https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG20/>.

¹⁹ Dash Bootstrap Components. "Official Website." Available online: <https://dash-bootstrap-components.opensource.faculty.ai/>.

Figure 8. Homepage tab

Risk Assessment: This page visualises the COVINFORM Risk Index on a choropleth map. Countries are colour-coded according to their quintile (as discussed in [Ranking \(Section 7.7\)](#)), which are calculated using the risk scores quintiles generated using both arithmetic and geometric aggregation. Users may select a year, domain, and aggregation function (arithmetic or geometric) to provide further visualisation of the risk model. Each country is coloured based on its corresponding quintile value, representing its risk level. Clicking on a country displays essential information, including the risk score, quintile, rank, country, and relevant indicators. A bar chart overlay shows the quintile trends for the selected country across all available years.

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Figure 9. Risk assessment tab

Geospatial Plots: This page visualizes annual datasets on a choropleth map. Users can select a year using a slider and explore disaggregated data by defined criteria, when available (i.e., users can select subsets of the data based on some filters). For example, users can choose to visualise the value of an indicator for women aged 15-19 instead of the value for the total population. This provides insights into how the data is distributed across various categories, enabling a more comprehensive analysis. Each country is coloured based on the data value, and clicking on a country displays the exact data point, units, and data source. A bar chart overlay shows data trends for the selected country across all available years.

The screenshot shows the COVINFORM web interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links: Homepage, Risk Assessment, Geospatial Plots, Indicator Comparisons, COVID-19 Trends, Case Study, and Knowledge Repository. Below the menu, a text prompt reads: "Select dataset and year below to display a Europe-wide map of data corresponding to the year and data in question." The interface includes several form elements:

- Dataset:** A dropdown menu set to "Age & Gender" with a close button (X).
- Download Dataset (Raw):** A button.
- Disaggregations:** Four dropdown menus. The first is "Age (Default: Total)", the second is "Sex (Default: Total)", and the last two are "N/A".
- Download Dataset (Disaggregated):** A button.
- Years:** A horizontal timeline slider from 2014 to 2021, with 2021 selected.
- Show/Hide Search Options:** A blue button.

 At the bottom of the form, the text "Age & Gender - Number of Individuals (Total)" is displayed.

Figure 10. Geospatial Plot – Dataset and Disaggregation selectors

Figure 11. Geospatial Plot – Choropleth Plot

Indicator Comparisons: This page enables users to visualise, for a single country, two annually reported datasets, plotting one against the other. This allows for a comparison between the two datasets, providing insights into their relationships and trends over time.

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Figure 12. Indicator Comparisons - Scatter plot

COVID-19 Trends: This page generates two plots with daily and weekly time series of COVID-19 specific data, mostly epidemiological indicators. Disaggregation options are also available, and users can select to visualise data for one country or compare trends of two countries against each other.

Figure 13. COVID-19 trends – Scatter and Line plots

Case Study: This page offers information about the COVINFORM case studies. Users can select the case study of interest through a dropdown menu. The Case Study page provides descriptions of the study population, research objective, and lessons learned from each study. It also includes an image of a group of people, depicting the case study population, with speech bubbles. Users can click on the speech bubbles to reveal individual quotes, selected by the researchers directly from the case study interviews.

The screenshot displays the COVINFORM Case Study tab for "Migrant Nurses in Wales in times of COVID-19". The page features a navigation bar with links to Homepage, Risk Assessment, Geospatial Plots, Indicator Comparisons, COVID-19 Trends, Case Study, and Knowledge Repository. The main content area includes a "Case Study Location" dropdown menu set to "Wales".

The study details are as follows:

- Study Population:** BAME overseas qualified Nurses who have worked in Welsh hospitals during the pandemic, and whose family largely lives in their country of origin.
- Research Objective:** To investigate how COVID-19 and its responses affect the experiences of vulnerable groups; particularly those who have living conditions that are arguably diverging mobile lives, such as working in and living in homes facilitated by healthcare facilities, such as hospitals, and being separated from family whilst working in jobs that are relatively high-risk due to the exacerbated threat of COVID-19 infection.

A central diagram illustrates the system architecture, showing the relationship between Business Systems and Units (BSU), Innovation Area (IA), Business (B), and Active Systems (AS). The diagram is divided into four main sections:

- Business Systems and Units (BSU):** Includes metrics like the number of hospitals, registered patients, and staff, as well as the number of COVID-19 cases and the impact of the pandemic on the Welsh economy.
- Innovation Area (IA):** Focuses on communication campaigns across healthcare and social media.
- Business (B):** Addresses challenges such as recruitment and staffing, infection control, and patient safety.
- Active Systems (AS):** Involves the role of qualified nurses, the impact of the pandemic on the Welsh economy, and the role of the Welsh government in supporting the NHS.

Below the diagram, the "Lesson Learnt" section highlights two key findings:

- The outcomes of the study will shed a light on health inequalities and structural intersectional issues (including race, gender, mobility, access to Welsh society).
- Provide new insights into these intersecting vulnerabilities to inform public health policy and its formation in Wales at a variety of governmental levels.

The page concludes with an illustration of healthcare workers in a "RED ZONE" and a footer indicating funding from the European Union's H2020 research & innovation programme.

Figure 14. Case study tab

Knowledge Repository: This page provides a simple search engine for unstructured data (e.g., deliverables, papers, policy briefs) produced or gathered as part of the COVINFORM project. Search can be performed either on document names or authors, and searches conducted either on all data or for a selected category. Searches can also be conducted using any relevant keyword. The document name and URL to access said data is then displayed below the search box.

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The screenshot displays the COVINFORM Knowledge Repository interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links: Homepage, Risk Assessment, Geospatial Plots, Indicator Comparisons, COVID-19 Trends, Case Study, and Knowledge Repository. Below the navigation, there is a search section with the following elements:

- A search prompt: "Select to search either Document Name or Authors" with an information icon.
- A search input field labeled "Document Name" with a clear button (x) and a dropdown arrow.
- A section titled "Select which document type of unstructured data to search" with three filter boxes:
 - "All Document Types" with a clear button (x) and a dropdown arrow.
 - "All Years" with a clear button (x) and a dropdown arrow.
 - "All Topics" with a clear button (x) and a dropdown arrow.
- A search input field labeled "Enter search text" with the placeholder "Search the COVINFORM Knowledge Repository".

Below the search section, there are three search results for bi-monthly reports:

- Bi-monthly report 01 – COVID-19 Vaccines: History and Facts**
By Elena Ambrosetti, Marina Zannella, Diotima Bertel, Su Anson, Alberto Hernández Tejedor
<https://www.covinform.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/39/2021/01/COVINFORM-Bi-Monthly-Report-01-A4-1.0.pdf>
- Bi-monthly report 02 – COVID-19 vaccination campaign in COVINFORM countries: infographics & best practices**
By Elena Ambrosetti, Marina Zannella, Itamar Laist, Chaim Rafalowski
<https://www.covinform.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/39/2021/03/COVINFORM-Brochure-A4-Bi-Monthly-Report-2.pdf>
- Bi-monthly report 03 – A Glimpse of the Lessons Learned During the COVID-19 Pandemic**
By Dailia Antunes, José Manuel Palma-Oliveira
<https://www.covinform.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/39/2021/06/COVINFORM-Brochure-A4-Bi-Monthly-Report-3.pdf>

At the bottom of the page, there is a footer with the European Union logo and the text: "This project has received funding from the European Union's H2020 research & innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101016247."

Figure 15. COVID-19 Resources – Knowledge Repository tab

10 Software implementation

The data preprocessing and modelling was done in both Microsoft Excel and Python programming software, using standard libraries for data processing together with custom libraries developed by Trilateral leveraging STRIAD, Trilateral's in-house cloud analytics solution. The software is securely stored on Trilateral's cloud code repository which uses a Git-based code management solution for version control of the codebase, ensuring changes can be tracked easily and any issues diagnosed rapidly. Raw data at various stages of processing are stored on the COVINFORM data lake, built on AWS S3 bucket. The dashboard was developed utilising Dash, a Python web framework that leverages both Python and JavaScript programming. Our dashboard is hosted on an EC2 instance provided by Trilateral - the code running on this instance utilises a Docker build of the application, which leverages containerisation technology to enable streamlined deployment, scalability, and isolation of the dashboard. This approach ensures that the dashboard can automatically restart as needed. Both Conda (an open-source cross-platform package manager and environment management system) and Python's default package manager are used to manage dependencies. Additionally, Conda is employed to create isolated environments specifically for data science projects. Features and fixes are developed using the Agile methodology, employing two-week sprints. This approach fosters an interactive and incremental development process, facilitating adaptability and flexibility to accommodate changes.

11 Next steps

The final evaluation workshop (Task 2.5) will be conducted by partner SINUS in September 2023. This workshop will focus on gathering feedback from external end-users to further refine the dashboard features and the presentation of the COVINFORM Risk Index. We anticipate that these activities will

lead to minor adjustments to the labelling and descriptive information presented with the Risk Index. In the next two months the effort will be focussed on finalising the dashboard functionalities, including accessibility and usability requirements. A major effort will be put into defining adequate ways to display on the dashboard the results of the risk modelling and identifying most effective visualisations to communicate countries' risk and vulnerability with the COVINFORM Risk Index and its broken-down risk scores. The effectiveness of these visualisations as well as the overall value of the COVINFORM dashboard as a tool for risk assessment will be evaluated during the final evaluation workshop. The remaining qualitative data will be derived from the case study analysis and will be available on submission of D3.8 Final Case Study Reports and Comparative Report – Update, in September 2023 [M35]. Finally, the dashboard link will be embedded into the COVINFORM Projects website, and the accompanying user guide will be added as a supporting document.

12 Conclusions

This report provides a final progress update on technical activities related to the development of the COVINFORM risk assessment tool and interactive dashboard to map the response and impact in the EU27 MS and the UK. The risk assessment framework has been further refined based on data preprocessing results, such as evaluations of interdependence between indicators. New data requirements pertaining to the collection of data for UK indicators required extensive review and processing to ensure comparability to data collected across the EU27 MS. Hence this report also provides an update on the data collection activities (Task 2.1) that have been carried out after submission of D2.1 and details on the final risk framework adopted. The statistical approach taken to standardise indicators prior to modelling the subdomains and domain scores have been described. In addition, the risk modelling approaches and justifications for the selected statistical model were discussed. The technology and deployment strategy for building the geo-spatial visualisation dashboard (Task 2.3) have been reported and the final considerations from evaluation workshops as part of Task 2.5 continue to be integrated. In the final months, WP2 activities will focus on deploying the risk index together with validating the model's outcome. Lastly, the remaining data collection activities relating to the qualitative case study data will be available and integrated based on predefined criteria in September 2023.

13 References

Andrews, N., Stowe, J., Kirsebom, F., Toffa, S., Rikeard, T., Gallagher, E., ... & Lopez Bernal, J. (2022). Covid-19 vaccine effectiveness against the Omicron (B. 1.1. 529) variant. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 386(16), 1532-1546.

Ganin, A. A., Quach, P., Panwar, M., Collier, Z. A., Keisler, J. M., Marchese, D., & Linkov, I. (2020). Multicriteria decision framework for cybersecurity risk assessment and management. *Risk Analysis*, 40(1), 183-199.

M. Robnik-Sikonja and I. Kononenko. Theoretical and empirical analysis of Relief and ReliefF. *Machine Learning*, 53:23–69, 2003.

Roloff, R. (2020). COVID-19 and No One's World. *Connections*, 19(2), 25-37.

Trump, B. D., & Linkov, I. (2020). Risk and resilience in the time of the COVID-19 crisis. *Environment Systems and Decisions*, 40(2), 171-173.

Wolff, S., & Ladi, S. (2020). European Union responses to the Covid-19 pandemic: Adaptability in times of permanent emergency. *Journal of European Integration*, 42(8), 1025-1040.

Žak, M., & Garncarz, J. (2020). Economic policy towards the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic in selected European Union countries. *International Entrepreneurship Review*, 6(4), 21-34.

Marvel SW, House JS, Wheeler M, et al. The COVID-19 Pandemic Vulnerability Index (PVI) Dashboard: Monitoring County-Level Vulnerability Using Visualization, Statistical Modeling, and Machine Learning. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2021;129(1):17701. doi:10.1289/EHP8690

Annex

Annex 1: COVINFORM – Risk Assessment Framework Data Sources

Definitions and reporting metadata for framework indicators

This document reports the data included in the COVINFORM Risk Assessment Framework. The Framework is composed of four domains (Threat, Vulnerabilities, Consequences and Resilience), and each domain is comprised of up-to four sub-domains, containing relevant indicators. This report provides information pertaining to the indicator attributes (e.g., reporting period, data source and format) and the scientific justification for inclusion. Where possible the original reporting format is described, or the reporting format that will be presented in the geospatial plots (i.e., cumulative COVID-19 case rate as opposed to daily). As described in this report D2.7., data was normalised for risk modelling activities.

Domain 1: THREAT (RISK OBJECT)

Sub-domain 1.1: Virus (cases)

COVID-19 Case Rate (weekly), Positivity Rate (%), Testing Rate

From the start of COVID-19 pandemic, the WHO's Emergency Programme implemented a global COVID-19 surveillance system²⁰. Widespread coronavirus testing, caused by infection with severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), allowed for monitoring of disease over countries and across population groups. SARS-CoV-2 surveillance was fundamental in understanding the evolution of the virus, the risk factors for severe disease and the impact of vaccination and public health and social measures.

To provide an overview of the epidemiological situation of the COVID-19 pandemic, health organisations reported weekly and daily COVID-19 statistics to track the number of COVID-19 cases, as per International Health Regulations (IHR 2005) requirements²¹. The 7-day rolling average offers easy visualisation of the number of new COVID-19 cases and allows for simple calculation of the rate of change overtime. In addition, weekly averages were adopted by many health agencies to improve the accuracy of reporting due to operational factors (e.g., delays in laboratory analysis and reporting).

In addition to case rate, knowing the testing rate can indicate the level of surveillance activity in a country, and the proportion of positive tests can indicate the intensity of transmission.

Note: Guidance on testing was routinely updated as the pandemic evolved and testing capacity intensified²². Data users should be cognisant that testing strategies across European countries and the UK varied widely, from screening programmes to diagnostic tests in health care settings. In addition, total counts do not support cross country comparisons and should be analysed using per population rates.

²⁰ <https://www.who.int/emergencies/overview>

²¹ <https://www.who.int/health-topics/international-health-regulations>

²² <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/WHO-2019-nCoV-SurveillanceGuidance-2022.2>

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Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>COVID-19 Case Rate</i>
Reporting period	2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Daily and Cumulative
Definition and Reporting criteria	Cases per 1,000 population
Source/s	EU 27MS & UK – Our World Data

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>COVID-19 Positivity Rate (%)</i>
Reporting period	2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Daily and Cumulative
Definition and Reporting criteria	100 x Number of new confirmed cases/number of tests done
Source/s	EU 27MS & UK – Our World Data

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>COVID-19 Testing Rate</i>
Reporting period	2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Daily and Cumulative
Definition and Reporting criteria	Tests per 1,000 population
Source/s	EU 27MS & UK – Our World Data

Sub-domain 1.2: Variant of concern

Early in the COVID-19 pandemic, the number of ‘mutant’ variant viruses was low due to the relatively small number of infections, so there were less opportunities for mutations to emerge. For that reason, reporting of COVID-19 variants in national surveillance began in September 2020. Since then, the vast number of infections, has led to the evolution of multiple SARS-CoV-2 variants. For COVID-19 variants, clear evidence is available indicating a significant impact on transmissibility, severity and/or immunity that is likely to have an impact on the epidemiological situation. The COVINFORM project is interested in all variants of concern (VoC) over the course of the pandemic, that resulted in increased transmissibility²³. These are labelled by transmission characteristics, either observed as community level transmission or dominant transmission (ibid.). For reporting, the WHO label (i.e., Alpha) is preferred as users will be less familiar with the variant code (i.e., B.1.1.7).

Note: ECDC regularly assesses new evidence on variants detected through epidemic intelligence, rules-based genomic variant screening, or other scientific sources. If a decision is made to add, remove, or change the category for any variant, the tables are updated to reflect this change.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Variants of Concern</i>
Reporting period	2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Weekly
Definition and Reporting criteria	Distribution of COVID-19 cases by Variant of Concern (VoC), No. Of detections and % of Variants EU - Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Delta, Omicron BA.1, Omicron BA.2 + L452X, Omicron BA.2, Omicron BA.4, Omicron BA.5 ^{24,25}
Source/s	EU 27MS - ECDC UK – gov.uk

Sub-domain 1.3: Likelihood of development

Mobility Index

Because COVID-19 is highly infectious, decreasing social interaction and community movement have been important public health approaches to lower COVID-19 transmission rates. Following recommendations to limit movements, governments across Europe and in the UK imposed

²³ <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/covid-19/variants-concer>

²⁴ Variants of concern as of 25 May 2022

²⁵ SARS-CoV-2 variants of concern as of 21 Aug 2022

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formal, stricter, and frequently legally mandated restrictions on people's freedom of movement²⁶. These restrictions included "stay at home" orders, the closure of non-essential retail and schools, and the prohibition of sporting events and other public gatherings.

Google Community Mobility Reports aimed to provide insights into what changed in response to these policies. The reports charted movement trends over time by geography, across different places such as retail and recreation, groceries and pharmacies, parks, transit stations, workplaces, and residential homes.

Google mobility data shows how visitors to (or time spent in) certain places changed compared to 'baseline days'. Baseline day represents a normal (pre-COVID-19) value for that day of the week. It is the median value from the 5-week period prior to the pandemic, 3 Jan – 6 Feb, 2020.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Mobility Index</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	26 MS and UK (Missing: Cyprus)
Reporting format	Daily
Definition and Reporting criteria	Compares mobility for the report date to the baseline day
Source/s	EU 26 MS & UK – Google Mobility Data

International Trade

In a globalised world, trade can drive various factors that contribute to the transmission of viruses, such as a country's social interactions, economic possibilities, and mobility patterns. An early case study from Italy suggested that over time, confirmed COVID-19 cases had a strong correlation with trade (Bontempi, E., & Coccia, M. 2021). The results implied that total imports and exports are a complex indication of COVID-19 disease transmission that outperforms other widely used parameters, such as economic, demographic, environmental, and climatic characteristics, in explaining the COVID-19 spread (ibid.).

In the COVINFORM Risk Framework, we consider the degree of trade in which a country engages to be a probable indicator of disease transmission and the likelihood of development overtime. Trade data published by Eurostat measures the value and quantity of goods traded between the EU Member States²⁷. Following the withdrawal of the UK from the EU on 31 Jan 2020, the UK were no longer legally obliged to share any trade data to Eurostat from the end of 2020. Pending an agreement on statistical cooperation between the EU and the UK, Eurostat will not publish any new data for the UK (ibid.). For

²⁶ <https://www.oecd.org/coronavirus/policy-responses/the-territorial-impact-of-covid-19-managing-the-crisis-across-levels-of-government-d3e314e1/>

²⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/6842948/11003521/Availability_of_UK_trade_data_after_BREXIT_FAQs.pdf/ce8cc509-8429-943f-5de3-a5d20cd33344?t=1614360113585

this reason, a UK data source was selected for the COVINFORM project, so to evaluate the degree of change overtime within the UK. The UK data was converted from British Pounds Sterling to Euros using the average exchange rate for the year considered²⁸.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>International Trade</i>
Reporting period	EU 2021 – 2021, UK- 1997-2021
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS - Trade balance in million (EURO) UK – Trade balance in GBP (Converted to EURO)
Source/s	EU 27 MS - Eurostat UK – Office of National Statistics

Other mobility data: International Sea and Air travel

As described above, mobility data has a significant impact on COVID-19 virus transmission. To capture the degree of mobility across countries, modes of transport beyond land travel were also integrated. Specifically, data regarding the number of passengers by sea or air, and the number of airports per capita are included.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>International Air Travel - Passengers</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS – Number of International Air Travel Passengers and UK – - EU and Other International Terminal Passenger Traffic
Source/s	EU 27 MS - Eurostat UK – Civil Aviation Authority

²⁸ <https://www.exchangerates.org.uk/GBP-EUR-spot-exchange-rates-history-2019.html>

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Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>International Sea Travel - Passengers</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS – Total number of International Sea Passengers UK - Total number of International and Domestic (to include Northern Ireland and British Isles) Sea Passengers
Source/s	EU 27 MS - Eurostat UK – gov.uk

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Airports</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS – Commercial airports per capita UK - Commercial airports per capita
Source/s	EU 27 MS - Eurostat UK - Civil Aviation Authority

Housing concentration

Overcrowded housing is a sociodemographic variable associated with increased infection rates from communicable diseases²⁹. It was widely observed that those of low socioeconomic status (SES), e.g., those with low household income, living in overcrowding dwellings and low education, were more vulnerable to COVID-19 morbidity and mortality (Khanijahani et al., 2021, Public Health England, 2020). Public health interventions to prevent and stop the spread of SARS-CoV-2 were slow to consider the risk of infection transmission for people living in overcrowded households and suitable interventions to reduce the risk of infection transmission (Soltan et al., 2021).

²⁹ WHO Housing and Health Guidelines: web Annex A. Accessed 15 March 2023. URL: <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/275838>

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Housing Concentration - Overcrowding</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS – Percentage of the population living in an overcrowded household UK (England only)- The data is an average for the 3 years from April 2018 to March 2021. This is to make sure there are enough households to be able to make reliable generalisations.
Source/s	EU 27MS - Eurostat - EU-SILC survey UK (England Only) – gov.uk – English Housing Survey

Pollution

Scientists worked to identify the environmental conditions that might have aided the spread of the SARS-Cov-2 virus. SARS-CoV-2 is an airborne virus, meaning the most common route of transmission is the spread of pathogens through the respiratory system by infected subjects and the penetration into the receiving host by inhalation.

For many viruses, atmospheric particulate matter (PM) would serve as a transport vector. The Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) defines PM as a group of particles that have been dispersed in the air for long enough to be diffused and transported³⁰. PM fosters a microenvironment favourable to a virus' persistence, therefore it is possible that it boosted SAR-CoV-2 viral transmission in respiratory aerosol. Environmental pollution, specifically PM, was evaluated by numerous scientists as one of the potential key contributors to the spread of COVID-19 (Comunian et al., 2020).

Based on these premises, we decided to include the PM10 annual average of the mean daily concentration as a factor influencing enhanced virus transmission.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Pollution</i>
Reporting period of interest	2019, 2020, 2021

³⁰ <https://www.epa.gov/pm-pollution/particulate-matter-pm-basics#PM>

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Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Daily
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK – PM10 annual average of the mean daily PM10 concentration
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK – European Environmental Agency

Temperature

Other viruses, like flu viruses and other coronaviruses, are known to be affected by environmental factors. For example, high temperatures and low humidity reduce the transmission of respiratory droplets, preventing the spread of flu. High temperatures are also known to inactivate other coronaviruses in the air and on surfaces. The relationship with SARS-CoV-2 spread and temperature has been explored and researchers have reported that countries were expected to see a decline in new COVID-19 cases during summer and a resurgence during colder months (Notari 2021; Wang 2020; Pawar 2020). This is likely due to higher temperatures and more intense UV radiation in summer more than would support compliance to public health measures to contain SARS-CoV-2 (Chen 2021). Imperial College London were one of the first research groups to incorporate environmental data into epidemiological models of the transmission of SARS-CoV-2 (Smith et al, 2021). They found that, to a certain extent, temperature could significantly change COVID-19 transmission. Their work suggests that lower autumn and winter temperatures may lead to the virus spreading more easily in the absence of policy interventions or behavioural changes.

To factor in periods of low temperature during the COVID-19 pandemic, the COVINFORM project obtained mean daily temperature data from each Metrological Headquarter in the 27 MS and the UK. In order to demonstrate comparability, the data was computed to a binary variable, reporting the proportion of days in which a country had a daily average temperature of less than 15 degrees (typical average autumn temperature or lower).

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Temperature</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Annual Average
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK – Proportion of days per year where average temperature is less than 15oC. Mean of daily mean temperatures.
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK – European Climate Assessment & Dataset

Age of population

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Age</i>
Reporting period	2019, 2020, 2021
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Age (years) (groups)
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS – Age of population UK – Age of population (groups - <15; 16-64; 65+)
Source/s	EU 27 MS – Eurostat UK - OECD

Ratio between the population over 60 and the total population to consider this vulnerability factor, even if it shows only relatively small differences from one region or country to another.

COVID-19 vaccination rate

An effective immunisation rollout offered the most promising prospect of reducing morbidity, mortality and overcoming the COVID-19 pandemic³¹. Studies also suggested some benefit of vaccination and vaccine boosting in reducing transmission of COVID-19^{32,33,34}. Public health officials and policymakers created strategic vaccine-acceptance communications to ensure wide vaccine³⁵. Once the rollout commenced, the scale and rate of vaccination was reported routinely by national public health surveillance agencies and included information on the total number of vaccinations administered and daily population coverage³⁶.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>COVID-19 vaccination rate</i>
Reporting period	2020, 2021

³¹ Le, T. T., Andreadakis, Z., Kumar, A., Román, R. G., Tollefsen, S., Saville, M., & Mayhew, S. (2020). The COVID-19 vaccine development landscape. *Nat Rev Drug Discov*, 19(5), 305-306.

³² Tan, S.T., Kwan, A.T., Rodríguez-Barraquer, I. *et al.* Infectiousness of SARS-CoV-2 breakthrough infections and reinfections during the Omicron wave. *Nat Med* 29, 358–365 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-022-02138-x>

³³ <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-022-02328-0>

³⁴ Eyre, D. W., Taylor, D., Purver, M., Chapman, D., Fowler, T., Pouwels, K. B., ... & Peto, T. E. (2022). Effect of Covid-19 vaccination on transmission of alpha and delta variants. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 386(8), 744-756.

³⁵ Chou, W. Y. S., & Budenz, A. (2020). Considering emotion in COVID-19 vaccine communication: addressing vaccine hesitancy and fostering vaccine confidence. *Health communication*, 35(14), 1718-1722.

³⁶ Mathieu, E., Ritchie, H., Ortiz-Ospina, E., Roser, M., Hasell, J., Appel, C., ... & Rodés-Guirao, L. (2021). A global database of COVID-19 vaccinations. *Nature human behaviour*, 5(7), 947-953.

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Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Daily
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK – COVID-19 Vaccine Rate (% population)
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK – Our World Data

Domain 2: VULNERABILITIES*Sub-domain 2.1: Physical*Hospital beds, Intensive Care Unit beds and Residential beds

Healthcare organizations needed to quickly create surge capacity, defined as the ability of healthcare services to increase their operations in response to a crisis to safely treat an increased inflow of patients. The pandemic's increasing demand directly impacted the limited resources on which healthcare services are built, such as employees and goods, as well as structure and system. Health or physical vulnerability in the COVINFORM risk assessment framework includes both healthcare capacity and the level of clinical vulnerability to COVID-19 at a population level. COVID-19 brought to light the necessity for a sufficient number of hospital beds and flexibility in their usage (i.e., ventilation and intensive care beds), as well as a sufficient number of medical professionals (doctors and nurses) with the necessary training to deliver the necessary care³⁷.

Healthcare vulnerabilities can be measured using various metrics and was closely monitored by public health bodies and healthcare organisation over the COVID-19 pandemic. Hospital bed and ICU bed capacity are common healthcare resource metrics to monitor the ability to provide care to inpatients³⁸. ICU beds are defined as beds with critical care equipment (e.g., ventilator) that are adequately staffed by specialized nurses and physicians with critical care training. Hospital beds are defined as beds regularly maintained, staffed, and available for use in public, private, general, and specialized hospitals and rehabilitation centres³⁹.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Hospital Beds</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Annual Average

³⁷ Ji, Y., Ma, Z., Peppelenbosch, M. P., & Pan, Q. (2020). Potential association between COVID-19 mortality and health-care resource availability. *The Lancet global health*, 8(4), e480.

³⁸ Berger, E., Winkelmann, J., Eckhardt, H., Nimptsch, U., Panteli, D., Reichebner, C., Rombey, T., & Busse, R. (2022). A country-level analysis comparing hospital capacity and utilisation during the first COVID-19 wave across Europe. *Health policy (Amsterdam, Netherlands)*, 126(5), 373–381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthpol.2021.11.009>

³⁹ <https://www.oecd.org/coronavirus/en/data-insights/intensive-care-beds-capacity>

Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK – Hospital beds (per 100,000 inhabitants)
Source/s	27 MS – Eurostat UK - OECD

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>ICU Beds</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Annual Average
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– ICU beds (per 100,000 inhabitants)
Source/s	Multiple sources across EU 27 and UK - A country-level analysis comparing hospital capacity and utilisation during the first COVID-19 wave across Europe The variability of critical care bed numbers in Europe OECD

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Residential Care Beds</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Annual Average
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK – Beds in nursing and residential care facilities (per 1,000 inhabitants)
Source/s	EU 22 MS & UK – OECD 5 MS - Eurostat

Medical (Frontline) Staff

During the COVID-19 pandemic the volatility of the public health crisis resulted in intense pressures for healthcare staff, and many healthcare workers were required to deliver care in specialist

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environments (i.e., ICU) beyond their primary training⁴⁰. To accurately determine the number of medical staff within certain specialisms or care settings during the course of the COVID-19 pandemic may be impossible but data has been reported across the EU MS and the UK.

Doctors

Data for this indicator come from the Eurostat data 'physicians by medical speciality'. As outlined in the dataset metadata⁴¹, physicians are classified in three main categories: *generalist medical practitioners*, *specialist medical practitioners* and *medical doctor not further defined*.

Nurses and care professionals

Nurses are defined as all the "practising" nurses providing direct health services to patients, including self-employed nurses. However, for some countries, due to lack of comparable data, the figures correspond to "professionally active" nurses, including nurses working in the health sector as managers, educators, researchers, etc.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Doctors</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Annual Average
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– Doctors (per 100,000 inhabitants)
Source/s	EU 27 MS – Eurostat UK - OECD

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Nurses</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Annual Average
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– Nurses (per 100,000 inhabitants)
Source/s	EU 27 MS – Eurostat UK - OECD

⁴⁰ Bergman, L., Falk, A. C., Wolf, A., & Larsson, I. M. (2021). Registered nurses' experiences of working in the intensive care unit during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Nursing in critical care*, 26(6), 467-475.

⁴¹ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/Annexes/hlth_res_esms_an1.pdf

Older Adults and Pre-Existing Health Conditions

Older people and people with chronic pre-existing conditions were reported to be at higher risk of severe COVID-19 disease leading to hospitalisation, admission to intensive care, and death⁴². Diseases posing an increased clinical risk included diabetes, obesity, hypertension, history of heart failure, ischaemic heart disease, cancer, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), chronic respiratory disease, chronic kidney disease, and immune compromised status. In addition, older age was also reported by global health agencies to be a factor for severe COVID-19 outcomes⁴³, with the greatest proportion of COVID-19 related deaths in older populations⁴⁴.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Pre-existing health conditions</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Annual Average
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– Longstanding health condition (% population)
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK - EUROSTAT

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Older adults</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Annual Average
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– Ratio of adults aged over 60 years
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK - EUROSTAT

Sub-domain 2.2: Social

Education Level

⁴² <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/infectious-disease-topics/z-disease-list/covid-19/facts/clinical-features-and-sequelae>

⁴³ <https://www.who.int/europe/news/item/03-04-2020-statement-older-people-are-at-highest-risk-from-covid-19-but-all-must-act-to-prevent-community-spread>

⁴⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/rtd/items/680700/en>

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Observational studies report that the severity of COVID-19 depends not only on physical conditions as mentioned above but also social determinants of health, such as lower incomes and lower educational level among various populations. In the European population, lower education level was associated with a higher risk of severe COVID-19 cases and COVID-19-related mortality^{45,46}. In part, due to behavioural characteristics, such as an inability to adapt working conditions and therefore reduce physical contact.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Education level</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS - Low levels of educational attainment (ISCED 2011 classification) UK – Percentage of population whose highest level educational attainment is less than NQF level 2 or above
Source/s	EU 27 MS - EUROSTAT UK – GOV.UK

Urban vs. Rural and Population Density

Population density and infrastructure played a key role in the transmission and effects of SARS-CoV2 in terms of morbidity and mortality. In the EU and UK, densely populated urban areas were the hardest hit in the first half of 2020, but as social distancing measures were introduced, rates dropped^{47,48}. However, from mid-2020 rural areas were seen to be impacted to a larger extent. Various reasons were attributed to increased risk in rural areas, specifically limited access to public health and specialist medical professionals⁴⁹, higher proportions of older dwellers⁵⁰ and limited digital infrastructure impacting remote working⁵¹.

⁴⁵ Drefahl, S., Wallace, M., Mussino, E., Aradhya, S., Kolk, M., Brandén, M., ... & Andersson, G. (2020). A population-based cohort study of socio-demographic risk factors for COVID-19 deaths in Sweden. *Nature communications*, 11(1), 5097.

⁴⁶ Lüdecke, D., & Von Dem Knesebeck, O. (2020). Protective behavior in course of the COVID-19 outbreak—survey results from Germany. *Frontiers in public health*, 8, 572561

^{47,28} Tammes, P. (2020). Social distancing, population density, and spread of COVID-19 in England: a longitudinal study. *BJGP open*, 4(3).

⁴⁸ Medica, M. (2020). COVID-19 mortality rates in the European Union, Switzerland, and the UK: effect of timeliness, lockdown rigidity, and population density.

⁴⁹ Apostolopoulos, N., Liargovas, P., Sklias, P., & Apostolopoulos, S. (2021). Healthcare enterprises and public policies on COVID-19: Insights from the Greek rural areas. *Strategic Change*, 30(2), 127-136.

⁵⁰ Kashnitsky, I., & Aburto, J. M. (2020). COVID-19 in unequally ageing European regions. *World development*, 136, 105170.

⁵¹ Esteban-Navarro, M. Á., García-Madurga, M. Á., Morte-Nadal, T., & Nogales-Bocio, A. I. (2020, December). The rural digital divide in the face of the COVID-19 pandemic in Europe—recommendations from a scoping review. In *Informatics* (Vol. 7, No. 4, p. 54). MDPI.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Rural vs. Urban</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– Population by sex, age, citizenship, labour status and degree of urbanisation
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK - EUROSTAT

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Population density</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS - Population density by NUTS 3 region UK– Population density
Source/s	EU 27 MS - EUROSTAT UK – World Bank

Gender

Whilst men were more likely to be infected with SARS-CoV-2 and more likely to die from it⁵², women's lives were more greatly affected in terms of social consequences. A report by the Institute for Fiscal Studies found that mothers in the UK were 15 times more likely than fathers to have either quit their job or lost it during the lockdown⁵³. Women are more likely to be “essential workers”, approximately 76% of care workers in the EU are women, 82% of supermarket cashiers and 95% of domestic cleaners and home help, are women⁵⁴. In addition, during the COVID-19 pandemic, and with the introduction of “lockdowns”, more women lost their lives to domestic violence⁵⁵.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Gender - % female</i>

⁵² Pérez-López, F. R., Tajada, M., Savirón-Cornudella, R., Sánchez-Prieto, M., Chedraui, P., & Terán, E. (2020). Coronavirus disease 2019 and gender-related mortality in European countries: A meta-analysis. *Maturitas*, 141, 59–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.maturitas.2020.06.017>

⁵³ <https://www.local.gov.uk/age-and-gender-impact-covid-19>

⁵⁴ <https://eige.europa.eu/newsroom/covid-19/essential-workers>

⁵⁵ <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/headlines/society/20201119STO92007/orange-the-world-no-to-violence-against-women>

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Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS - Population on 1 January by age and sex UK - National mid-year population estimates for the UK and its constituent countries by administrative area, age and sex
Source/s	EU 27 MS - EUROSTAT UK – ONS

Immigration Status

Research from several countries have revealed a much greater risk of infection and adverse outcomes from COVID-19 among Black, Asian, and Minority Ethnic (BAME) groups⁵⁶, compared to the native white population in the same countries⁵⁷. These adverse outcomes are likely the result of a complex interaction of socioeconomic disadvantage influencing exposure to SARS-CoV-2 and underlying health status, that predisposes to severe illness⁵⁸.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Immigration Status</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS - Immigration by age group, sex and level of human development of the country of citizenship UK - Long-term international immigration
Source/s	EU 27 MS and UK - EUROSTAT UK - ONS

Civic Participation

Civic participation is the involvement of members of society or communities in local, state, and national government. It can include voting, activism, volunteering, and community engagement but

⁵⁶ Bhatia, M. (2020). COVID-19 and BAME Group in the United Kingdom. The International Journal of Community and Social Development, 2(2), 269-272.

⁵⁷ Hargreaves, S., Hayward, S. E., Noori, T., McKee, M., & Kumar, B. (2021). COVID-19: counting migrants in. The Lancet, 398(10296), 211-212.

⁵⁸ Hayward, S. E., Deal, A., Cheng, C., Crawshaw, A., Orcutt, M., Vandrevala, T. F., ... & Hargreaves, S. (2021). Clinical outcomes and risk factors for COVID-19 among migrant populations in high-income countries: a systematic review. Journal of migration and health, 3, 100041.

at the simplest level, “freedom of opinion and expression is effectively guaranteed”⁵⁹. The level of civic participant became increasingly important during the COVID-19 pandemic⁶⁰. Bottom-up approaches, where the community is a resource and an active partner, became critical for building trust and addressing inequalities, particularly in terms of COVID-19 vaccine uptake and compliance to social interventions^{61,62}.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Civic Participation</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– Degree of Civic Participation (%)
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK – World Justice Project – WORLD BANK

Sub-Domain 2.3 Economic

Economic vulnerability can be defined as ‘*the risk a country faces when encountering a shock*’⁶³.

Gross Domestic Product - purchasing power parities (GDP-PPP)

GDP is a measure of the strength of a country’s economy. Defined as ‘*the total monetary or market value of all the finished goods and services produced within a country in a specific time period*’⁶⁴. There are various reporting metrics for GDP, however, ‘purchasing power parities’ (PPP) allows for comparison across countries. PPPs are ‘*price relatives that show the ratio of the prices in national currencies of the same good or service in different countries*’⁶⁵.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Gross Domestic Product</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK

⁵⁹ https://worldjusticeproject.org/sites/default/files/documents/ROLIndex2017-2018_Variables_FINAL.pdf

⁶⁰ Waeterloos, C., De Meulenaere, J., Walrave, M., & Ponnet, K. (2021). Tackling COVID-19 from below: civic participation among online neighbourhood network users during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Online information review*, 45(4), 777-794.

⁶¹ Jalloh, M. F., Nur, A. A., Nur, S. A., Winters, M., Bedson, J., Pedi, D., Prybylski, D., Namageyo-Funa, A., Hageman, K. M., Baker, B. J., Jalloh, M. B., Eng, E., Nordenstedt, H., & Hakim, A. J. (2021). Behaviour adoption approaches during public health emergencies: implications for the COVID-19 pandemic and beyond. *BMJ global health*, 6(1), e004450. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2020-004450>

⁶² Waeterloos, C., De Meulenaere, J., Walrave, M., & Ponnet, K. (2021). Tackling COVID-19 from below: civic participation among online neighbourhood network users during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Online information review*, 45(4), 777-794.

⁶³ Noy, I., & Yonson, R. (2018). Economic vulnerability and resilience to natural hazards: A survey of concepts and measurements. *Sustainability*, 10(8), 2850.

⁶⁴ <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/g/gdp.asp>

⁶⁵ <https://www.oecd.org/sdd/prices-ppp/purchasingpowerparities-frequentlyaskedquestionsfaqs.htm>

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Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– GDP – PPP (constant, 2017)
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK – WORLD BANK

Poverty

The COVID-19 pandemic exposed to a greater extent the vulnerability of poor populations. Poverty interacts with health in many ways and research has shown that those living in poverty are more likely to have chronic illnesses⁶⁶. In addition, poverty impacts a person's resilience, straining their capabilities and opportunities⁶⁷.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Poverty</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– % At risk of poverty
Source/s	EU - EUROSTAT UK – GOV.UK

Income Inequality

Income is also associated with health: people in the bottom 40% of the income distribution are almost twice as likely to report poor health than those in the top 20%⁶⁸. Early findings reported by Frank Elgar et al., (2020) demonstrated through time series analysis showed that COVID-19-related mortality was positively related to income inequality, trust and confidence in state institutions⁶⁹.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Income Inequality</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK

⁶⁶ Callander, E. J., Schofield, D. J., & Shrestha, R. N. (2013). Chronic health conditions and poverty: a cross-sectional study using a multidimensional poverty measure. *BMJ open*, 3(11), e003397.

⁶⁷ Bénédicte, C., Newsham, A., Davies, M., Ulrichs, M., & Godfrey-Wood, R. (2014). Resilience, poverty and development. *Journal of international development*, 26(5), 598-623.

⁶⁸ Tinson, A. (2020). Living in poverty was bad for your health before COVID-19. The Health Foundation.

⁶⁹ Elgar, F. J., Stefaniak, A., & Wohl, M. J. (2020). The trouble with trust: Time-series analysis of social capital, income inequality, and COVID-19 deaths in 84 countries. *Social science & medicine*, 263, 113365.

Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– Inequality of income distribution (S80/S20 ratio)
Source/s	EU 27 MS – EUROSTAT UK - ONS

Employment by Industry

Those in precarious employment, characterised by poorly paid employment, employment insecurity (e.g., temporary or zero-hour contracts), and limited rights and protection, were greatly impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic⁷⁰. Women, migrant workers, low skilled workers, and young people are more likely than others to be precariously employed⁷¹. Many employees experienced cycles of employment, and then unemployment, especially during times of lockdown⁷².

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	Employment by Industry – Industries most at-risk
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– Industries known to be affected by COVID-19 policy measures - Arts and Recreation, Construction, Accommodation and Food, Transport and Storage and Wholesale and Retail
Source/s	EU 27 MS – EUROSTAT UK - ONS

Sub-domain 2.4: Information

Information and communication inequalities are mediating factors in the exacerbated health disparities observed in vulnerable groups during the pandemic. The following factors were considered important in understanding the level of access populations had to public health information; and as a tool to reduce social isolation during times during lockdowns.

Digital Skills and Access

⁷⁰ Matilla-Santander, N., Ahonen, E., Albin, M., Baron, S., Bolibar, M., Bosmans, K., ... & All Members of the PWR Study Consortium. (2021). COVID-19 and precarious employment: consequences of the evolving crisis. *International Journal of Health Services*, 51(2), 226-228.

⁷¹ Julià, M., Vanroelen, C., Bosmans, K., Van Aerden, K., & Benach, J. (2017). Precarious employment and quality of employment in relation to health and well-being in Europe. *International Journal of Health Services*, 47(3), 389-409.

⁷² <https://australiainstitute.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/Shock-Troops-of-the-Pandemic.pdf>

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Societal differences in access and use of digital technologies are commonly referred to as the ‘digital divide’ and disproportionately affect the health of disadvantaged communities such as ethnic minorities, rural populations, the elderly and residents of care homes⁷³. Lower levels of digital access and skills further isolated vulnerable populations and increased health risks as community-based healthcare delivery largely moved to a telehealth model (ibid.).

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Digital Skills</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– % Individuals with low levels of digital skills
Source/s	EU 27 MS – EUROSTAT UK - IPSOS
Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Digital Access</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– % Access to Household ICT
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK– EUROSTAT

Trust in Government

The level of trust in the communication actors was a key determinant in compliance to public health measures⁷⁴. Furthermore, research has shown a direct and indirect association of good governance practices and the public's trust in government via perceived government response on COVID-19⁷⁵. Results also showed that government agency's delivery of quality information on social media positively shapes public trust in government (ibid.).

⁷³ Ramsetty, A., & Adams, C. (2020). Impact of the digital divide in the age of COVID-19. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 27(7), 1147-1148.

⁷⁴ Shanka, M. S., & Menebo, M. M. (2022). When and how trust in government leads to compliance with COVID-19 precautionary measures. *Journal of Business Research*, 139, 1275-1283.

⁷⁵ Mansoor, M. (2021). Citizens' trust in government as a function of good governance and government agency's provision of quality information on social media during COVID-19. *Government information quarterly*, 38(4), 101597.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Trust in Government</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Bi-annual (except for 2020 where only one survey was conducted)
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– Do you tend to trust or not trust your National Government? %
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK– EUROSTAT

Domain 3: CONSEQUENCES

Sub-domain 3.1: Physical/Health

Excess mortality

Excess mortality is a term used in epidemiology that refers to the number of deaths from all causes during a crisis above and beyond what would be expected to see under ‘normal’ conditions⁷⁶. In this case, we’re interested in how the number of deaths during the COVID-19 pandemic compares to the deaths that would have been expected had the pandemic not occurred.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Excess mortality</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Daily
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS– Cumulative deaths from all causes compared to projection based on previous years (per million people)
Source/s	EU 27 MS and UK– Our World in Data

Hospital Occupancy and ICU admissions (COVID-19-related)

The direct impact of COVID-19 on healthcare systems was closely monitored during the pandemic, using key resource metrics (i.e., hospital bed occupancy rates). Public health officials closely monitored this data to identify a drop in the system’s capacity (i.e., bed shortages), which in turn prompted government responses (i.e., lockdown measures)⁷⁷.

⁷⁶ <https://www.kingsfund.org.uk/blog/2023/03/when-death-excess-death-getting-behind-numbers>

⁷⁷ Verelst, F., Kuylen, E., & Beutels, P. (2020). Indications for healthcare surge capacity in European countries facing an exponential increase in coronavirus disease (COVID-19) cases, March 2020. *Eurosurveillance*, 25(13), 2000323.

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Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Hospital Occupancy – COVID-19</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Weekly/Daily
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– Data on hospital occupancy for COVID-19
Source/s	EU 27 MS – ECDC UK - ONS

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>ICU Occupancy – COVID-19</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Weekly/Daily
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK - Data on ICU admission rates and current occupancy for COVID-19
Source/s	EU 27 MS – EUROSTAT UK – GOV.UK

COVID-19 related deaths

The ultimate consequence of the COVID-19 pandemic is the loss of life. COVID-19 was ranked as a leading cause of death; and at certain times, it was the leading cause of death⁷⁸. Mortality risk was determined by age, with the risk of COVID-19 death highest in older adult populations and lowest in the young (ibid). Definitions and reporting of COVID-19-related deaths varied across EU member states and the UK, particularly in the early stage in the pandemic. Such as whether someone ever had a positive test, had one within a defined period before death, or did not have a test but had symptoms consistent with COVID-19⁷⁹

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>COVID-19 related deaths</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK

⁷⁸ <https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jama/article-abstract/2774464>

⁷⁹ Karanikolos, M., & McKee, M. (2020). How comparable is COVID-19 mortality across countries?. *Eurohealth*, 26(2), 45-50.

Reporting format	Daily
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– Number of confirmed deaths from COVID-19
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK– Our World in Data

Sub-domain3.2: Social

Food Insecurity

A person is considered “food secure” when they have the physical, social, and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life⁸⁰. COVID-19 threatened food security in some developed countries and further impacted human security⁸¹.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Food Insecurity</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the total population (%)
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK– FAO

Crime

The COVID-19 pandemic and government responses to limit social contact have had a significant impact on patterns of crime⁸². Certain police reported crimes have declined, such as household burglaries, however, there has been increased reporting of domestic violence⁸³ and online fraud. Survey conducted in the UK have shown the crime patterns returned to typical incidence rates following lockdown periods⁸⁴.

Attribute	Description
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⁸⁰ https://www.fao.org/fileadmin/templates/faoitally/documents/pdf/pdf_Food_Security_Cocept_Note.pdf

⁸¹ <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/cread/article/view/202191>

⁸² Nivette, A.E., Zahnow, R., Aguilar, R. *et al.* A global analysis of the impact of COVID-19 stay-at-home restrictions on crime. *Nat Hum Behav* 5, 868–877 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-021-01139-z>

⁸³ Bradbury-Jones, C., & Isham, L. (2020). The pandemic paradox: the consequences of COVID-19 on domestic violence. 2020. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 12.

⁸⁴ <https://blog.ons.gov.uk/2021/11/04/understanding-the-impact-of-the-pandemic-on-levels-of-crime-in-england-and-wales/>

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Indicator name	<i>Violent Crime rates</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– Police recorded crimes
Source/s	EU 27 MS – EUROSTAT UK– ONS , GOV.SCOT , PSNI

Loss of Education

Beyond health-related consequences, one of the most notably impacts of the pandemic was the loss of education in children. The full extent of the disruption in learning and development will only be understood in the coming decades. Before the end of 2020 the Department for Education (UK), found a learning loss of up to 2 months in reading in both primary and secondary pupils, based on assessments of more than 400,000 pupils⁸⁵. Again, and as per the compounded vulnerability of those already living precariously, the lack of educational progress made is proportionally greater in children living in persistent poverty, attributable to a lack of digital access and technology, and adequate home supports⁸⁶.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Loss of Education</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Daily
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– School closures and supports for IT
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK– UNICEF

Sub-domain 3.3: Economic

The pandemic has impacted the economy in many ways, as described above. Lockdown restrictions, temporary closure of businesses to limit movement, the economic impact has been severe⁸⁷, and many countries are experiencing financial crises⁸⁸. The following indicators have been incorporated

⁸⁵ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/pupils-progress-in-the-2020-to-2022-academic-years>

⁸⁶ <https://epi.org.uk/publications-and-research/education-in-england-annual-report-2020/>

⁸⁷ Pak, A., Adegboye, O. A., Adekunle, A. I., Rahman, K. M., McBryde, E. S., & Eisen, D. P. (2020). Economic consequences of the COVID-19 outbreak: the need for epidemic preparedness. *Frontiers in public health*, 8, 241.

⁸⁸ <https://cepr.org/voxeu/columns/eu-economy-after-covid-19-implications-economic-governance>

into the COVINFORM risk assessment framework, to quantify the economic consequences in Europe and the UK.

Unemployment Rates

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Unemployment rates</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS - Unemployment by sex, age and duration of unemployment (1 000) UK– Unemployment rate (aged 16 and over, seasonally adjusted): %
Source/s	EU 27 MS – EUROSTAT UK– ONS

Reduced Income

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Reduced income</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– Median Household Disposable Income (PPP)
Source/s	EU 27 MS – Eurostat UK - ONS

Social Protection

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Social Protection Spending</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly

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Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK – Total expenditure on social protection benefits by type (% of GDP)
Source/s	EU 27 MS - EUROSTAT UK - OECD

Sub-domain 3.4: Environmental

As reported OECD, the COVID-19 pandemic and implemented responses have significant effects on economic activity and the structure of the economy⁸⁹. The latter plays a key role in how economic effects translate into effects on environmental pressures. The environmental consequences that are linked to energy use seen a decline in 2020 of 7-8%, followed by a recovery to 2-3% below the pre-COVID baseline projection (ibid). This includes emissions of Greenhouse Gases, air pollutants and fossil fuel materials use.

Other environmental pressures have a different set of economic influence, and have a notable pattern of impacts. Emissions of particulate matter (PM2.5), which includes black carbon and organic carbon, are linked to transport (heavily affected) and residential activities (less affected) (ibid.). Both GHG emissions and PM2.5 have been included in the COVINFORM risk assessment model.

Exposure to Pollution

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Particulate Matter (PM2.5)</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK– Fine particulate matter (PM2.5)
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK - EEA

Greenhouse Gas Emissions

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Greenhouse Gases</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK

⁸⁹ <https://www.oecd.org/coronavirus/policy-responses/the-long-term-environmental-implications-of-covid-19-4b7a9937/>

Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK – Greenhouse gas emissions (tonnes per capita)
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK – Our World Data

Domain 4: RESILIENCE

Resilience is “the ability of a system or organization to react to and recover from disturbances at an early stage, with minimal effect on the dynamic stability”⁹⁰. Resilience involves the ability of a complex system to absorb the “shocks” gracefully and rebound in a controlled manner to a level of performance equivalent of beyond pre-disturbance (ibid.).

Sub-domain 4.1: Ability to recover

Government Health Spending

Given the COVID-19 pandemic shocked the healthcare systems across the world, the level of investment prior to and during the pandemic directly influences their ability to recover.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Government Health Spending</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK – Compulsory Government Health Spending (% GDP)
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK - OECD

Investments - Gross fixed capital formation

GFCF dropped dramatically across all EU countries and the UK during the pandemic, although with different intensities across MS⁹¹. The economic policy responses mitigated the impact of the pandemic and supported recovery. Total investment in EU countries declined due to high uncertainty in the economy. And household savings and household financial net worth have increased, while the impact

⁹⁰ Johnsen S. (2010). Resilience in Risk Analysis and Risk Assessment. Critical Infrastructure Protection IV: Fourth Annual IFIP WG 11.10 International Conference on Critical Infrastructure Protection, ICCIP 2010, Washington, DC, USA, March 15-17, 2010, Revised Selected Papers, 342, 215–227. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-16806-2_15

⁹¹ Licchetta, M., & Meyermans, E. (2022). Gross Fixed Capital Formation in the Euro Area During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Intereconomics*, 57(4), 238–246. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10272-022-1058-1>

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of the crisis on household debt has been limited (ibid.). These averages, however, mask divergent trends, with both wealth and savings increasing faster among the wealthy⁹².

Gross fixed capital formation (GFCF), also called "investment", is defined as the acquisition of produced assets.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Investment – Gross fixed capital formation</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK – Gross fixed capital formation (% of GDP)
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK – World Bank

Government Debt

Government finances offer an indication of the health of national economies. The COVID-19 pandemic drove economic recessions globally in 2020 however by 2021, deficits began to decline again⁹³. The economic slump caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, resulted in a drop in GDP and the expenditure measures to contain the economic and social impact of the pandemic had a strong impact on the EU MS and UK economic profile and ability to recover (ibid.).

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Government Debt</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK – Consolidated general government gross debt at nominal value, outstanding at the end of the year (%GDP)
Source/s	EU 27 MS - EUROSTAT UK - ONS

Corruption Perception Index (CPI)

⁹² <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/sites/4d28b126-en/index.html?itemId=/content/component/4d28b126-en>

⁹³ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Government_finance_statistics#Introduction

The CPI ranks countries around the world by their perceived levels of public sector corruption, scoring on a scale of 0 (highly corrupt) to 100 (very clean). Corruption affects governments' ability to protect citizens and reduces public trust, resulting in increased and more difficult-to-control security concerns.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Corruption Perception Index</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Yearly
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK – CPI Score (0-100)
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK – Transparency.org

Vaccine Affordability

Vaccine equity means that vaccines should be allocated across all countries based on needs and regardless of their economic status. Globally, the distribution of vaccines is shaped by challenging political, economic, social, diplomatic, and health-related matters. Therefore, accurate and up-to-date data and information are critical components in guiding the understanding of vaccine equity and highlight blind spots.

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Vaccine Affordability</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	No time period specified
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK – Cost of vaccinating 40% of population as percent of current health expenditure (CHE) per capita in US\$
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK – UNDP.org

Sub-domain 4.2: Ability to Adapt

Economic and Public Health Measures

COVID-19 has had a significant impact on global public health and economies. To appropriately respond, a number of containment and mitigation measures were implemented, with the goal of mitigating surges of patients in hospitals and safeguarding the most vulnerable persons from infection, including the elderly and those with co-morbidities. Strategies for achieving these targets vary, but they are typically based on national risk assessments, which include estimates of the number of patients requiring hospital admission. A list of economic measures (e.g., income support, rent

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freezes, tax credits) and health measures (e.g., masks, curfew, domestic lockdown, state of emergency).

Attribute	Description
Indicator name	<i>Economic and Public Health measures</i>
Geographic Coverage	27 MS and UK
Reporting format	Daily
Definition and Reporting criteria	EU 27 MS & UK – Intensity of non-pharmaceutical health interventions in response to COVID-19 pandemic. Global score based on policies for masks, curfew, domestic lockdown, state of emergency
Source/s	EU 27 MS & UK – Response2covid.org